

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 4

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UDK: 616.36-002.951.21-089

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ANALYSIS OF RELAPSE OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS AND THE ROLE OF MORPHOLOGICAL MODIFICATION

For citation: Rakhmanov E. Kosim, Davlatov S. Salim, Radjabov P. Jasur. Analysis of relapse of liver echinococcosis and the role of morphological modification // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 4, pp.76-82

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13709879>

ABSTRACT

To formulate the impact of the morphological forms of echinococcal cysts on the frequency of relapses of the disease, we conducted a retrospective analysis of surgical protocols and found that in 93 (36.9%) operated patients the morphological structure of the cysts corresponded to modifications of their type, such as: hominis, in 128 (50.8%); echinococcus veterinorum and in echinococcus acephalocystis, similarly 31 (12.3%). Moreover, of the 47 patients with relapse of this disease, 29 (61.7%) had morphological signs corresponding to echococcus hominis in 18 (38.3%); No relapses were detected in those operated on with the morphological structure of echinococcus acephalocystis and echinococcus veterinorum corresponding. Thus, out of 93 patients operated on for liver echinococcosis with a morphological structure corresponding to the form of echinococcus hominis, relapse of the disease was observed in 29, i.e. in 31.2%, out of 128 patients operated on with morphological modification of echinococcus veterinorum cysts in 18, i.e. in 14.1%, a relapse of echinococcosis also developed in the long term after surgery.

Key words: liver echinococcosis, morphological modification disease recurrence.

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JIGAR EXINOKOKKOZI QAYTALANISHINING TAHLILI VA MORFOLOGIK MODIFIKATSIYANING O'RNI

ANNOTATSIYA

Exinokokk kistalari morfologik shakli ko'rishiga ko'ra kasallikning qaytalanish chastotasiga ta'siri va undagi vujudga keladigan o'zgarishlarni qayd qilish uchun jarrohlik protokollarining retrospektiv tahlili o'tkazildi va amaliyot bajarilgan 93 (36,9%) bemorda kistalarning morfologik tuzilishi exinokokk modifikatsiyasiga mos kelishini aniqladik. Shunga ko'ra echinococcus hominis, 128 (50,8%) - echinococcus veterinorum va 31 (12,3%) - echinococcus acephalocystis. Bundan tashqari, kasallikning qaytalanishi bilan og'rigan 47 bemorda 29 (61,7%) da echinococcus hominisga mos keladigan morfologik belgilar, 18 (38,3%) morfologik tuzilish bilan operatsiya qilinganlarda echinococcus acephalocystisda esa retsediv aniqlanmagan. Shu bilan birgalikda, echinococcus hominis shakliga mos bo'lgan morfologik ko'rishga ega bo'lgan jigar exinokokkozi bilan jarrohlik amaliyoti bajarilgan 93 nafar bemordan 29 nafarida, ya'ni. 31,2% da kasallikning qaytalanishi kuzatilgan, 128 nafar bemorda echinococcus veterinorum kistalarining morfologik modifikatsiyasi bilan jarrohlik amaliyotini bajarilgan, 18 nafarida, ya'ni. 14,1% ham operatsiyadan keyin uzoq muddatda takroriy exinokokkozni rivojlantirdi.

Kalit so'zlar: jigar exinokokkozi, morfologik modifikatsiya, kasallikning qaytalanishi.

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АНАЛИЗ РЕЦИДИВА ЭХИНОКОККОЗА ПЕЧЕНИ И РОЛЬ MORFOLOGICHESKOY MODIFIKACII

АННОТАЦИЯ

Для формулировки воздействие морфологических форм эхинококковых кист на частоту рецидивов заболевания мы провели ретроспективный анализ хирургических протоколов и установили, что у 93 (36,9%) прооперированных больных морфологическая структура кист соответствовала модификациям их виду, таких как: hominis, у 128 (50,8%); echinococcus veterinorum и у echinococcus acephalocystis аналогично 31 (12,3%). При этом из 47 больных с рецидивом данного заболевания у 29 (61,7%) были морфологические признаки, соответствующие echinococcus hominis у 18 (38,3%); у оперированных с морфологической структурой echinococcus acephalocystis и echinococcus veterinorum соответствующей рецидивов не выявлено. Так, из 93 больных, оперированных по поводу эхинококкоза печени с морфологической структурой, соответствующей форме echinococcus hominis, рецидив заболевания наблюдался у 29, т.е. у 31,2%, из 128 больных, оперированных с морфологической модификацией echinococcus veterinorum кисты у 18, т.е. у 14,1%, также развился рецидив эхинококкоза в отдаленные сроки после операции.

Ключевые слова: эхинококкоз печени, морфологическая модификация, рецидив болезни.

Dolzarlighi. Jahon Sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, exinokokkoz butun dunyo bo'ylab 1 milliondan ortiq odamga ta'sir qiladi, 44-84% hollarda turli organlar va to'qimalar orasida bu jarayon jigarda lokalizatsiya qilinadi [5, 6, 7]. Bemorlar sonining pasayish tendensiyasi yo'qligi va kasallanish darajasi 100 000 aholi orasida 1,2 dan 9,0 gacha o'zgarib turadigan endemik mintaqalar mavjudligi sababli, bu parazitlar kasallik jiddiy tibbiy va ijtimoiy muammo bo'lib qolmoqda [4].

Hozirgi bosqichda, jigar exinokokkozi (JE) tashxisi axborot qiymati yuqori bo'lgan noinvaziv ko'rish usullari tufayli 95-100% [1] ga yetadi, muhim qiyinchiliklar mavjud emas. Biroq, exinokokkozga nisbatan hushyorlikning yetishmasligi kech tashxis qo'yishga va natijada kasallikning murakkab shakllarining ko'payishiga yordam beradi [2, 3]. Operatsiyadan keyingi asoratlarni (34-50%) va kasallik (15-64%) operatsiyadan keyingi kasallikning qaytalanish holatlari keng tarqalgan jarrohlik taktikasini kam samaradorligini [7] va ishonchliligini ko'rsatadi.

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqqan holda, ushbu xavfli kasallikning oldini olish va davolash bo'yicha ma'lumotlarni takomillashtirish va yangi samarali chora-tadbirlarni ishlab chiqish zarurligi ayon bo'ladi.

Tadqiqot maqsadi. Exinokokk kistalarining morfologik modifikatsiyasiga qarab takroriy jigar exinokokkozining mumkin bo'lgan sabablarini tahlil qilish.

Tadqiqot materiallari va usullari. Exinokokk bilan jigar shikastlanishining uchta morfologik modifikatsiyasi mavjud: *Echinococcus hominis*, *Echinococcus -veterinorum*, *Echinococcus acephalocystis*. Exinokokkoz kasalligini olib keluvchilarning morfologik modifikatsiyasini aniqlash uchun biz instrumental tadqiqot usullari (ultratovush tekshiruv, KT) natijalarini tahlil qildik va jigar exinokokkozi bo'lgan 252 nafar bemorda jarrohlik materialini o'rgandik. Exinokokkoz modifikatsiyalarining morfologik tuzilishini tavsiflashdan oldin shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, ularning barchasi germinal membranada sodir bo'ladigan distrofik jarayonlarning mavjudligi va rivojlanish darajasi bilan bir-biridan farq qiladi, bu yerda parazitning asosiy tarkibiy birligi- bu nasl kapsulasi hayotiy protoskolekslarni ishlab chiqarishga qodir.

Natijalar va ularning muhokamasi. *Echinococcus hominis* modifikatsiyasi exinokokk kistalarining 36,9% holatlarida qayd etilgan. Parazitning bu shakli kista ichida gidatid suyuqligidan tashqari protoskoleksli kapsulalarda qiz va ba'zan nevara pufagi borligi bilan ajralib turardi. Odatda bunday kistalar katta hajmga ega edi. Ona kistalari makroskopik jihatdan qo'pol sirtga ega bo'lib, sutli oq yoki oq-sariq rangga bo'yalgan (rasm 1, 2). Qiz kistalari soni birdan bir necha o'nlabgacha keng tarqalgan. Ona kistasining yiringlashi yoki o'limi bilan ularning bo'shlig'idagi qiz kistasi bir xil o'zgarishlarga uchradi. Biroq, katta exinokokk kistalarida qiz pufagi turli vaqtlarda nobud bo'ladi va shuning uchun o'liklar bilan birga tirik qiz pufagi topilgan. Ushbu kistalarda gidatid suyuqligining bosimi odatda past bo'ladi va suyuqlikning rangi shaffof yoki ko'pincha bulutli bo'ladi. Ona kistasi va yetuk qiz kistalari suyuqligini sitologik tekshirishda protoskolekslar aniqlandi.

Distrofik o'zgarishlar tabiatda fokal edi. Kista devorining turli joylari o'zgarishlarning zo'ravonligi bilan bir-biridan farq qilishi mumkin. Germinal membrananing shishishi va delaminatsiyasi membranalarning o'tkazuvchanligi buzilganligini ko'rsatadi. O'lik kistalarda germinal qatlamning erta o'limi qayd etiladi. Xitinli qobiq yanada barqaror va keyinchalik parchalanishga uchraydi. Parazitning bu shaklidagi xarakterli ultratovush belgisi "baliq tangachalari" alomati bo'lib, u ikki xil bo'lishi mumkin - tekislangan va yumaloq tangachalar. Birinchisi, "ko'p kamerali" exinokokk belgilari, ikkinchisi- kista involyusiyasi belgilari. *Echinococcus hominis* ning ultratovush semiotikasi 3-rasmda ko'rsatilgan.

Echinococcus hominis ni aniqlashning klinik ahamiyati shundan iboratki, o'limdan keyingi erta o'zgarishlar bosqichi bo'lib, aynan shu shaklda skolekslarning xitin qobig'idan tashqariga qalinlashganligi yoki hatto fibroz kapsuladan tashqariga ko'chishi sodir bo'ladi va exinokokk kistasining o'sishida ekzogen kurtaklanish bilan sodir bo'ladi.

Rasm. 1. 2. Jigarda Echinococcus hominis modifikatsiyasining morfologik shakli va ona kistasidan qiz va nevara kistalari olib tashlangan.

Rasm. 3. Echinococcus hominis qiz pufagining ultratovushli surati.

Operatsiyadan keyingi uzoq muddatli davrda exinokokkozni jarrohlik yo‘li bilan davolash natijalarini tahlil qilishimiz ushbu modifikatsiya bilan kasallikning qaytalanishi oldindan mavjud bo‘lgan kistalar o‘rnida kuzatilganligidan dalolat beradi. Shunday qilib, kasallikning 47 ta qaytalanishidan 29 tasi (61,7%) echinococcus hominis bilan zararlanish holatlari edi. Echinococcus veterinorum modifikatsiyasi parazitlar kistalarning 50,8% holatlarida qayd etilgan. Kasallikning ushbu shaklida lavrotsistalar ichida faqat nasl kapsulalari va exinokokk suyuqligi mavjud. Qiz pufakchalarining shakllanishi sodir bo‘lmaydi. Ushbu turdagi pufakchalarning o‘ziga xos xususiyati exinokokk suyuqligining boshqa shakllarga nisbatan eng yuqori bosimidir. Ko‘pgina hollarda, bunday kistalar klinik jihatdan "tarang" deb ta’riflanadi (Rasm. 4).

Rasm. 4. Jigarda echinococcus veterinorum ning "Tarang" exinokokk kistasi.

Exinokokk suyuqligining sitologik tekshiruvini exinokokk suyuqligida erkin suzuvchi ko'plab skolekslar va nasl kapsulalarini aniqlaydi. 1 ml suyuqlikdagi ularning soni o'rtacha 1200 gacha, mikroskopik skolekslar oval shaklga ega. Yorug'lik mikroskopi ostida ichki mikroorganizm qatlami ingichka bo'lib, pufak bo'shlig'ini ichkaridan qoplagan membrana shaklida bo'ladi. Ushbu qatlamning shishishi va delaminatsiyasi kamroq aniqlanadi. Germinal membrananing deyarli butun yuzasi qum donasiga o'xshash germinal qavatga donadorlik beradigan murtak pufakchalari qatlami bilan qoplangan.

Echinococcus veterinorum ham parazit mavjudligining agressiv shakli bo'lib, ko'p sonli hayotni ta'minlovchi skolekslarni o'z ichiga olgan gidatid suyuqligining yuqori bosimi tufayli qobiqning yaxlitligini ozgina buzgan holda erkin qorin bo'shlig'iga kirib, qorin bo'shlig'i organlarini massiv exinokokkoz bilan zararlanishiga olib keladi. Shuningdek, ushbu turdagi kistalarning o'ziga xos xususiyati exinokokk kistasi atrofida hosil bo'lgan qalin tolali kapsuladir. Shuning uchun ushbu modifikatsiya bilan jarrohlik aralashuvlar aparazitarlik va antiparazitarlik qoidalariga diqqat bilan rioya qilgan holda amalga oshirilishi kerak. Ushbu modifikatsiyadagi kistalarning operatsiyadan oldingi diagnostikasi bir qator bilvosita topilmalarga asoslanadi, buning asosida echinococcus veterinorum mavjudligini baholash ehtimoli ko'proq. Avvalo, bu "gidatid qum" bo'lib, u ultratovush yordamida sub'ekt tanasining holati o'zgarganda aniqlanadi. Ushbu exografik naqsh ko'plab skolekslar ona kistasining bo'shlig'ini to'ldirish va giperexogen cho'kindi sifatida namoyon bo'lish kabilarga sabab bo'ladi (rasm. 5).

Rasm. 5. Giperexogen cho'kindi borligi bilan echinococcus veterinorum da jigarining ultratovush tekshiruvini.

Kista modifikatsiyasi haqida bilvosita fikr berishi mumkin bo'lgan yana bir o'ziga xos xususiyat-bu tolali kapsulaning qalinligi. Bizning ma'lumotlarimizga tayangan holda, jigarining residiv (takroriy) exinokokkozi mavjud bo'lgan 47 nafar bemordan 18 (38,3%) nafarida echinococcus veterinorum morfologik tuzilishiga mos bo'lgan belgilarni ko'rsatdi. Parazitar kistalarning 12,3 foizida echinococcus acephalocystis uchunchi modifikatsiyasining lavrotsistalari aniqlandi. Ushbu turdagi kistalar zoti kapsulalari va protoskolekslarning yo'qligi bilan tavsiflanadi. Ular odatda diametri 6-7 sm dan oshmaydigan o'rta kattalikda edi, sarg'ish-kulrang rangga ega edi, silliq devor, tolali kapsulada farq qilardi, unchalik aniq emas edi.

Kistalarning gidatid suyuqligini sitologik tekshirish paytida skolekslar aniqlanmadi. Germinal membranani yorug'lik mikroskopi yordamida gistologik tekshirish shuni ko'rsatdiki, uning butun yuzasi distrofik o'zgarishlarga uchraydi, zoti kapsulalari mavjud emas. Shuning uchun bu kistalar germinal elementlarni ishlab chiqarishga qodir emas.

Bunday kistalarning exografik va kompyuter tomografik xususiyatlari parazit bo'lmagan jigar kistalariga juda o'xshaydi, chunki ularning tarkibi bir hil va tolali kapsulaning qalinligi katta o'lchamlarga yetib bormaydi.

Biz echinococcus acephalocystis parazit mavjudligining eng kam invaziv shakli ekanligini aniqladik. Kursning "qulayligi" exinokokk suyuqligida hayotiy elementlarning yetishmasligi tufayli past darajadagi agressivlik va past energiya salohiyatiga ega bo'lganligi sababli, kistalarning ushbu

modifikatsiyasi bilan tarqalgan exinokokkoz holatlari va kasallikning qaytalanishi mavjud emas. Bundan tashqari, ushbu turdagi kistalar katta o'lchamlarga yetib bormaydi va jigar tomonidan morfologik o'zgarishlar qaytariladi.

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, jigarning ko'plab exinokokk bilan zararlanishi 167 (66,2%) bemorda, alohida hollarda exinokokkozning turli modifikatsiyalarning birlashishi kuzatildi. *Echinococcus hominis* va *echinococcus veterinorum* assotsiatsiyasi kuzatildi.

Xulosa. Exinokokk kistalarining morfologik shaklining kasallik bilan kasallanishiga ta'sirini aniqlash uchun biz operatsiyalar protokollarini retrospektiv tahlil qildik va 93 (36,9%) operatsiya qilingan bemorlarda kistalarning morfologik tuzilishi *Echinococcus hominis* modifikatsiyasiga to'g'ri kelishini aniqladik, 128 (50,8%) – *echinococcus veterinorum* va 31 (12,3%) - *echinococcus acephalocystis*.

Bundan tashqari, kasallikning rivojlangan qaytalanishi bo'lgan 47 bemorda *echinococcus hominis* ga mos keladigan morfologik belgilar 29 (61,7%), *echinococcus veterinorum* 18 (38,3%) aniqlandi, *echinococcus acephalocystis* ga mos keladigan morfologik tuzilish bilan operatsiya qilinganlarda qaytalanish kuzatilmadi. Shunday qilib, *echinococcus hominis* shakliga mos keladigan morfologik tuzilishga ega jigar exinokokkozi mavjud bo'lgan jarrohlik amaliyoti bajarilgan 93 nafar bemordan 29 nafari, ya'ni 31,2 foizida kasallikning residivi kuzatilgan, *echinococcus veterinorum* kistalarining morfologik modifikatsiyasi bilan jarrohlik amaliyoti bajarilgan 128 nafar bemordan 18 nafari, ya'ni 14,1 foizida ham operatsiyadan keyingi muddatda uzoq vaqt davomida takroriy (retsediv) exinokokkoz rivojlangan.

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Статья поступила в редакцию 11.07.2024; одобрена после рецензирования 21.08.2024; принята к публикации 24.08.2024.

The article was submitted 11.07.2024; approved after reviewing 21.08.2024; accepted for publication 24.08.2024.

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Источники финансирования: Работа не имела специального финансирования.

Конфликт интересов: Авторы декларируют отсутствие явных и потенциальных конфликтов интересов, связанных с публикацией настоящей статьи.

Вклад авторов:

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Sources of funding: The work did not receive any specific funding.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no explicit or potential conflicts of interest associated with the publication of this article.

Contribution of the authors:

Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich - the ideological concept of the work, editing the article;

Davletov Salim Sulaimonovich - collection and analysis of literature sources, writing a text.

Radjabov Zhasur Pardabaevich - collection and analysis of literature sources

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 4

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